

Chiropractic BioPhysics® 46th Annual Convention

September 6–8, 2024

Tucson, AZ, USA

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Resolution of Cervicogenic Dizziness and Vasovagal Syncope in a 29-Year-Old Female With Neck and Back Pain and Disability Following Correction of Cervical Lordosis Using Chiropractic BioPhysics® Spinal Rehabilitation: A Case Report.

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Abstract

Objectives: To demonstrate a case of neck pain (NP), upper back pain (UBP), low back pain (LBP), cervicogenic dizziness, and vasovagal syncope reflex activated by cervical extension movement being resolved by Chiropractic BioPhysics® (CBP®) structural spinal rehabilitation.

Clinical Features: A 29-year-old female presented to a chiropractic office with intermittent NP and UBP and tension for 2 weeks that she rated 8/10 on a numeric rating scale (NRS) of 0 to 10 where 0 is no pain and 10 is maximum pain and chronic LBP. The patient stated that she has been taking birth control medication since 15 years of age and she is taking an antidepressant and blood pressure medication for hypertension as prescribed by her medical doctor (MD). Pre-treatment exam revealed cervical active range of motion (AROM) measuring: decreased for neck extension (-RxH) at 40° with dizziness, sweating, and syncope (normal is 70°) and decreased for right rotation at 70° (normal is 90°) with 3/10 pain in the right and left trapezii. Right and left cervical lateral flexion AROM was within normal limits (WNL) with 4/10 pain during right lateral flexion in the right trapezius and dizziness and 2/10 pain during left lateral flexion in the left trapezius. Thoracolumbar and neck flexion AROM were normal. The following orthopedic tests were positive yielding 2-4/10 pain: Jackson test on the left (2/10 pain) and right (4/10 pain), Shoulder Depressor test on the left (4/10 pain), George's maneuver (dizziness). The patient needed to lay down during the exam due to strong dizziness while performing cervical

extension.

Pre-treatment posture analysis was performed using PostureScreen® Mobile Posture Analysis (PostureCo, Inc., Trinity, FL, USA). The patient had abnormal posture including: right head translation (+TxH) and anterior head translation (+TzH) (Figure 1A & 2A). Pre-treatment neutral lateral cervical (NLC) radiographic examination analysis was performed using PostureRay® X-Ray Electronic Health Records Software (PostureCo, Inc., Trinity, FL, USA). Pre-treatment NLC radiograph shows: reversal of cervical lordosis (absolute rotational angle) from C2 to C7 (ARA C2-C7) measuring 9.4° (ideal is -42°), intervertebral posterior tangent angle (relative rotational angle) from C5 to C6 (RRA C5-C6) measuring 6.0° (ideal is -8°), and sagittal translation of C2 with respect to C7 (Tz C2-C7) measuring 23.8 mm (ideal is 0 mm) (Figure 3A).

Pre-treatment patient reported outcomes (PRO) included the Neck Disability Index (NDI) to assess the patient's self-reported NP and disability scoring 40% indicating moderate disability due to NP, a Oswestry Disability Index (ODI) to assess the patient's self-reported LBP and related disability scoring a 36% indicating moderate disability due to LBP.

Intervention & Outcomes: The patient received 68 in-office treatment sessions over 5 months including Diversified chiropractic manipulation and CBP® Mirror Image® (MI) corrective chiropractic adjustments, therapeutic exercises, and mechanical traction. MI therapies involve positioning the patient in a corrected or over-corrected postural position. MI adjustments involved positioning the patient in their opposite posture on a drop table to and applying adjustments manually, with drop ta and with an Impulse® Adjusting Instrument (Neuromechanical Innovations, Chandler, AZ, USA). During the first MI adjustment, the patient experienced the dizziness and syncope symptoms during cervical extension and the patient fainted twice that day. This confirmed that the patient was experiencing a vasovagal syncope reflex activated by cervical extension. Vasovagal syncope causes blood pressure and heart rate to drop suddenly reducing blood flow to the brain resulting in syncope. Based on this outcome, three steps were identified to prevent losing consciousness and were applied as a safety method during cervical extension in MI therapies:

1. Lie down with legs elevated 30 cm above the heart;
2. Make a fist and increase arm tension;
3. Wait until feeling better and then stand up slowly.

MI mechanical traction was performed using the 3-D Denneroll™ Traction Table System (Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotics, New South Wales, Australia) with a medium Cervical Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotic (Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotics, New South Wales, Australia) placed at the mid-to-lower cervical spine and a forehead strap holding the head on the table preventing head extension (Figure 4A).

At the 24th visit, a progress evaluation revealed the patient was able to perform cervical extension with no dizziness or syncope. As a result, MI exercises were added to the treatment regimen. Fedorchuk lordosis inducing procedure (FLIP) MI exercises were prescribed and involve:

1. Maximum +TzH which causes a coupling pattern of the cervical spine creating lordosis of the upper cervical spine and kyphosis of the lower cervical spine.
2. While maintaining +TzH, maximum -RxH which allows for the upper cervical spine to maintain its lordosis and for the lower cervical spine to move toward a healthy lordosis.
3. While maintaining the -RxH, posterior and inferior head translation (-TzH and -TyH) allowing for the head to return to a normal postural position while maintaining the induced cervical lordosis from previous movements.

MI traction was progressed by extending the patient's head over the medium cervical Denneroll™ and off of the table and then further with 4.5 kg hanging from her head with an upper strap to improve cervical curve (Figure 4B). The patient had their legs elevated 30 cm above her heart and would wait 3 minutes after every MI mechanical traction session before getting up. The patient was also prescribed +TxH combined with -TxT and -RxH MI exercises for coronal posture correction on a whole-body vibration (WBV) platform to increase blood circulation (Figure 4C). The patient was instructed to make a fist during the exercises to help prevent syncope or related symptoms.

Post-treatment posture analysis showed improvement in posture (Figure 1B & 2B). Post-treatment radiographic examination revealed improvement in: ARA C2-C7 -16.4°, RRA C5/6 to 1.5°, and Tz C2-C7 to 8.9 mm (Figure 3B). Post-treatment PROs revealed improvement in NDI to 0% indicating no disability due to NP and ODI to 2% indicating minimal-to-no disability due to LBP. The patient reported she no longer experiences dizziness or syncope during cervical extension.

Conclusion: The results of this case further validate that CBP® corrective chiropractic care is an effective method to treat

abnormal cervical curve and posture which has been shown to affect blood flow in the neck and brain and may be associated with vasovagal syncope. Improvement in the cervical curve may result in the resolution of vasovagal syncope and cervicogenic dizziness during normal movement. More research is needed involving spinal biomechanical analysis and rehabilitation in patients with vasovagal syncope and cervicogenic dizziness.

Figure 1A-B. Pre-Treatment and Post-Treatment Sagittal Posture

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal posture. The red lines represent the actual sagittal posture of the patient. The yellow dotted lines show the thoracic kyphosis and pelvic measurements.

Figure 2A-B. Pre-Treatment and Post-Treatment Coronal Posture

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal coronal posture. The red lines represent the actual coronal posture of the patient. The yellow circles with the black ring inside are anatomical landmarks made to analyze the patient's posture and the yellow dotted lines show the leg postural alignment.

Figure 3A-B. Pre-Treatment and Post-Treatment Neutral Lateral Cervical Radiographs

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal cervical spinal alignment. The red line represents the actual posterior tangent lines of the C2-T1 vertebrae.

Figure 4. A) Mirror Image® Traction Using 3-D Denneroll™ Traction Table System and Cervical Denneroll™, B) Mirror Image® Traction Using 3-D Denneroll™ Traction Table System, and C) Mirror Image® Exercise Using CBP® Pro-Lordotic Neck Exerciser and Whole-Body Vibration Platform

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Improvement in Chronic Neck Pain, Back Pain, and Quality of Life Following Correction of Primary Sagittal Plane Adult Spinal Deformity Using Chiropractic BioPhysics® Structural Spinal Rehabilitation in a 68-Year-Old Male with Prior Lumbar Spine Surgery: A Case Report and 3-Month Follow Up.

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Abstract

Objective: To present a case involving treatment of a patient with primary sagittal plane adult spinal deformity (ASD) and associated chronic low back pain (cLBP), chronic neck pain (cNP) and a decreased quality of life (QOL) utilizing corrective chiropractic care. ASD is associated with increased pain, disability, need for assisted living care, and mortality. Due to increasing prevalence of ASD, finding safe, non-invasive and cost-effective methods for reducing or correcting ASD is needed.

Clinical Features: A 68-year-old male presented to a chiropractic practice with chief complaints of chronic neck pain, mid-back pain, low back pain, and severe spinal stiffness & tightness. The patient reported that he has worked as a tow truck company owner and operator which he feels contributed to a long history of spinal stiffness and pain. He stated that his symptoms have been more frequent and more intense since 2016 when he suffered a lifting injury which resulted in an L2 disc herniation with fragmentation. He stated surgery was performed in 2016 due to severe LBP and bilateral leg numbness, tingling, weakness, and loss of bladder control. The patient states that surgery resolved the severe pain and most of the bilateral leg numbness, weakness, and tingling. However, since the surgery, the patient states he has had constant, dull, aching pain that he rated as a 6/10 using the numeric rating scale (NRS) for pain on a scale of 0-10 where 0 is no pain and 10 is maximum pain. Also, since surgery, he states he has been left with an inability to empty his bladder and needs to self-catheter when desiring to void urine. The patient states that activities of daily living (ADL) are provocative of his neck and back pain including working, walking, bending, twisting, lifting, and sustained sitting and standing. He reported frequent charley horse-type leg pain and cramping that interfered with sleep.

The patient completed a Short-Form 36 (SF-36) health-related quality of life (HRQOL) questionnaire to assess self-reported effects of the patient's ASD, cLBP, cNP on his HRQOL. The SF-36 is a 36-question survey that provides scaled scores for nine different HRQOL domains on a scale of 0 to 100, where 0 is the lowest HRQOL and 100 is the highest. Pre-treatment scores showed: Physical Functioning (PF) was 70, Role Limitations due to Physical (RPL) was 100, Role Limitations due to Emotional (RLE) was 100, Energy (E) was 60, Emotional Well-Being (EWB) was 72, Social Function (SF) was 50, Pain (P) was 67.5, General Health (GH) was 60 and Change in Health Status (Δ HS) was 50.

Pre-treatment posture examination and analysis was performed using PostureScreen® Mobile Posture Analysis (PostureCo, Inc. Trinity, FL, USA). The patient displayed severe anterior head & thorax translation (+TzH, +TxT), moderate anterior lumbar translation (+TzL) and an inability to look forward with his head fixed in downward flexion (+RxH) (Figure 1A).

Radiographic examination and analysis was performed using PostureRay® X-Ray Electronic Health Records Software (PostureCo, Inc., Trinity, FL, USA) revealed primary sagittal plane ASD with sagittal vertical axis from C7 to S1 (SVA C7-S1) measuring 70.7 mm (ASD diagnosis 50.0mm, ideal is 0 mm), anterior head translation from C2-C7 (Tz C2-C7)

measuring 46.7mm (ideal is 0 mm), absolute rotational angle from C2 to C7 (ARA C2-C7) measuring -16.8° (ideal is -42°), Tz T1-T12 measuring 45.6 mm (ideal is 0 mm), Tz T12-S1 measuring 35.0 mm (ideal is 0 mm).

Interventions & Outcomes: The patient was treated 30 times in-office over a duration of 10 weeks. Care consisted of traditional chiropractic adjustments and Chiropractic BioPhysics® (CBP®) corrective care protocols utilizing Mirror Image® (MI) chiropractic adjustments, spinal exercises, and mechanical traction.

For traditional chiropractic adjustments, Diversified technique was utilized, while Drop table adjustments and an IMPAC Pro-ArthroStim® Instrument (I.M.P.A.C. Inc., Salem, OR, USA) were utilized for the MI adjustments. MI exercises were performed by leaning back against the wall, contacting occiput, mid-back, and pelvis to achieve -TzH, -TzT, -TzL. In this position he performed heel raises for sets of 20 repetitions at 3-5 seconds per repetition. MI traction utilized the 3-D Denneroll™ Traction Table System (Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotics, New South Wales, AUS). The patient was placed supine on the table in -TzH, -TzT, -TzL, -TzP position with the pelvis strapped down over both ASIS to induce -RxP and the shoulders strapped down induce -TzT and -RxT, and a small Cervical Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotic (Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotics, New South Wales, Australia) placed at C6/7 to induce -RxH.

Home care prescriptions consisted of the following: MI exercises noted above and MI traction laying supine on floor with a 2-inch block under his pelvis in the -TzH, -TzT, -TzL, -TzP position with his legs elevated by resting on an ottoman and palms facing the ceiling for 15–20-minute sessions per day.

Post-treatment SF-36 showed PF was 75, RLP was 50, RLE was 100, E was 65, EWB was 72, SF was 75, P was 67.5, GH was 65, and Δ HS was 75. Post-treatment posture analysis revealed marked improvement in overall sagittal balance. Post-treatment radiographic examination revealed improvement in primary sagittal plane ASD SVA C7-S1 to 6.6 mm, Tz C2-C7 to 20.3 mm, ARA C2-C7 to -30.5° (ideal is -42°), Tz T1-T12 to 10.4 mm, and Tz T12-S1 to 5.7 mm.

As a result of the subjective and objective improvements, the patient decided to discontinue corrective care and was transitioned to supportive care on a reduced treatment frequency of two visits per month. Supportive care consists of traditional chiropractic adjustments and MI chiropractic adjustments and spinal exercises. He was advised to continue previously prescribed at-home MI spinal exercises and mechanical traction, three times per week.

A three-month follow-up evaluation was performed. Three-month follow-up posture and radiographic analysis revealed maintained improved spinal alignment and posture. Three-month SF-36 showed maintained or further improved HRQOL measures with significant improvements in SF (87.5), P (100), GH (85), and Δ HS (100).

Conclusion: The results of this case indicate that CBP® corrective chiropractic care is an effective method to treat primary sagittal plane ASD which contributes to cLBP, cNP and disability causing decreased HRQOL. Improvements in spinal alignment and posture may result in long term reduction or resolution of ASD, cLBP, cNP and improved HRQOL. This case study shows the need for more research involving spinal biomechanics and rehabilitation in patients with ASD, cLBP and cNP.

Figure 1A-C. Pre-Treatment, Post-Treatment and 3-Month Follow-Up Sagittal Posture Assessments

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal posture. The red lines represent the actual sagittal posture of the patient. The yellow circles with the black ring inside are anatomical landmarks made to analyze the patient's posture and the yellow dotted lines show the thoracic kyphosis and pelvic measurements.

Figure 2A-C. Pre-Treatment, Post-Treatment and 3-Month Follow-Up Lateral Full-Spine (Stitched Sectional) Radiographs

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal spinal alignment and posture. The red lines represent the actual C2-L5 posterior tangent lines of the patient.

Figure 3. A) Mirror Image® Exercises with IMPAC Pro-ArthroStim® Adjusting Instrument, B) Mirror Image® Adjustment with a drop table, and C) Mirror Image Traction Using 3-D Denneroll™ Traction Table System (Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotics, New South Wales, Australia)

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Successful Treatment of a 55-Year-Old Male with 15 Years of Chronic Low Back Pain With L1 Traumatic Compression Fracture Using Chiropractic BioPhysics® (CBP®) Corrective Spinal Rehabilitation: A Case Study with a 1-Year Follow-Up.

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Abstract

Objective: This case report presents the successful treatment of a 55-year-old male with chronic low back pain (cLBP) through the application of Chiropractic BioPhysics® (CBP®) techniques. The patient had previously experienced traditional chiropractic care involving adjustments only, due to limited options where he lived. The history of LBP was recurrent for 15 years following a 24-foot fall from a building resulting in a compression fracture of L1.

Clinical Features: The patient reported cLBP with pain from 6-9/10 depending on activity and duration of activity (on a scale of 0-10 where 0 is no pain and 10 is the worst pain imaginable). He reported increased pain with activities of daily living (ADL) such as standing, walking, climbing stairs, and sneezing and coughing (with radiating pain to the right leg above the knee). The initial Functional Rating Index (FRI) score was 34/40 (ideal is 0) on a scale of 0-40 where 0 is no functional impairment and 40 is maximum functional impairment. Posture analysis showed abnormal posture. Radiography exam and analysis showed posterior translation of T12 to S1 (TZ T12-S1) measuring -46.5 mm (ideal is 0 mm), thoracolumbar kyphosis from T12-L2 (ARA T12-L2) measuring 11.4° (ideal is -6°), segmental Tz L1-L2, L2-L3, and L3-L4 measuring -6.6 mm, -6.8 mm, and -6.6 mm (ideal is 0 mm), and a confirmed compression fracture at L1 (Figure 1A).

Intervention and Outcome: The patient underwent a CBP® corrective spinal rehabilitation treatment regimen of 100 sessions including Diversified, Cox Flexion/Distract, and CBP® Mirror Image® (MI) chiropractic adjustments, spinal exercises, and mechanical traction. The majority of these treatments were administered 2-3 times per day over the course of 2.5 months due to the patient traveling from out of town.

MI therapies are performed in the corrected or over-corrected position to retrain spinal alignment and posture towards a healthy, normal. MI adjustments were performed with the patient supine, placed in anterior thorax translation (+TzT) with the thoracolumbar spine extended (-RxT) over a foam bolster whereas Diversified adjustments were applied to the cervical spine. MI traction was conducted using a 3-D Denneroll™ Traction Table System (Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotics, New South Wales, Australia) positioning the patient supine in +TzT and the thoracolumbar junction -RxT over a Denneroll™ Thoracic Retrainer (Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotics, New South Wales, Australia) (Figure 2A). Straps held the ASIS in place while a round belt pulled the lower thoracic spine into -RxT over the Thoracic Retrainer. The patient increased the intensity of the +TzT and -RxT during each traction session (Figure 2B-C). MI exercises were performed seated in +TzT and -RxT with a CBP® Pro-Lordotic Neck Exerciser (Chiropractic BioPhysics®, Eagle, ID, USA) to strengthen the thorax and neck (Figure 3).

After 2.5 months of treatment, a re-exam was performed. The FRI score improved to 2/40 reflecting significant functional improvements and almost no functional impairment. Radiography exam and analysis showed improvements in ARA T12-L2 to 9.0° (ideal is -6°) and segmental Tz L1-L2, L2-L3, and L3-L4 measuring -3.5 mm, -4.5 mm, and -4.2 mm (ideal is 0 mm) (Figure 1B).

A one-year follow-up radiography exam demonstrated sustained improvements in the thoracolumbar kyphosis and lumbar spondylolistheses (Figure 1C).

Conclusion: The strategic application of multiple chiropractic techniques, including CBP® MI adjustments, spinal exercises, and mechanical traction resulted in improvements in spinal alignment and posture and concomitant improvements in pain and function underscoring the method's efficacy in treating complex cases of spinal dysfunction associated with trauma and biomechanical abnormalities. This case advocates for the broader adoption and investigation of these techniques within chiropractic practice to address similar clinical scenarios effectively.

Figure 1A-C. Pre-Treatment, Post-Treatment, and 1-Year Follow-Up Lateral Lumbar Radiographs

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal lumbar spinal alignment. The red lines represent the actual T12-L6 posterior tangent lines of the patient.

Figure 2. A) Mirror Image® Traction on the 3-D Denneroll™ Traction Table System, B) First MI Traction Progression, and C) Second MI Traction Progression

Figure 3. Mirror Image® Exercises Using a CBP® Pro-Lordotic

4

Significant and Sustained Improvement in Disability, Duration and Severity in a 64-Year-Old Male with Chronic Debilitating Spontaneous Vertigo After Unsuccessful Medical Approach: A Chiropractic BioPhysics® Case Report with 16-Month Follow-Up

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Abstract

Objectives: To report a case of significant and sustained improvement in chronic spontaneous vertigo using Chiropractic BioPhysics® (CBP®) treatment after unsuccessful traditional medical approach.

Clinical Features: A 64-year-old male visited a chiropractic clinic with 20 years of chronic debilitating vertigo. He was diagnosed with Ménière's disease due to a series of his symptoms including tinnitus, dizziness, vertigo and hearing loss.

He reported his vertigo symptoms were episodic every 6-12 months, each episode lasting for 2-4 weeks, 3-4 hours/day or every other day. He described the vertigo as debilitating and incapacitating and that he would be bedridden and discontinue any social or physical activities during the attacks and experience extreme fatigue after the attack.

He initially received a medical approach and was prescribed medications including Betahistine 24 mg 1x/day and Hydrochlorothiazide 50 mg 1x/day, a low salt diet, and elimination of alcohol and caffeine from his diet. He was then referred to an Eyes, Ears, Nose and Throat (EENT) specialist for an examination followed by magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) but the cause of his vertigo remained unknown with no improvement in symptoms.

Pre-treatment radiographs showed loss of cervical lordosis (ARA C2-C7) measuring -27° (ideal is -42°), increased thoracic kyphosis (ARA T1-T12) measuring 69° (ideal is 44°), and anterior sagittal vertical axis (SVA C1-S1) measuring 78 mm (ideal is 0 mm) (Figure 1). Pre-treatment posture analysis using PostureScreen® Mobile Posture Analysis (PostureCo, Inc., Trinity, FL, USA) showed anterior pelvis, posterior thorax, and anterior head posture (Figure 2A). Cervical range of motion (ROM) was measured using a goniometer and showed cervical left rotation measuring 70° (normal is 70°), right rotation measuring 50° (normal is 70°), left lateral flexion measuring 15° (normal is 40°), and right lateral flexion measuring 10° (normal is 40°).

Interventions and Outcomes: This patient performed CBP® Mirror Image® (MI) adjustments using an IMPAC Pro-ArthroStim® Instrument (I.M.P.A.C. Inc., Salem, OR, USA) 1x/week (Figure 3A & B), MI exercises using a CBP® Pro-Lordotic Neck Exerciser (Chiropractic BioPhysics®, Eagle, ID, USA) and a Thoracic Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotic (Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotics, New South Wales, Australia) 7x/week (Figure 3C & D), and multi-directional mechanical spinal traction 2x/week (Figure 3E), and Thoracic Denneroll™ traction 5x/week for 15 minutes (Figure 3F) over the course of 16 weeks while maintaining the same medication and diet recommendations.

After 16 weeks of corrective care, posture analysis shows improvement in posture (Figure 2B), and cervical ROM improved to 75° during left rotation, 75° during right rotation, 25° during left lateral flexion, and 25° during right lateral flexion. During the 16 weeks of care, the patient did not report any episodes of vertigo.

After the cessation of in-clinic treatment there was a follow-up with the patient over a period of 16 months. After 16 weeks of corrective care, this patient still maintained the use of thoracic Denneroll™ at home 1 day per week as reported. Posture analysis showed continued improvement in posture (Figure 3C) and cervical ROM improved further 35° during left lateral flexion and 35° during right lateral flexion. He reported two vertigo episodes in May 2023 and May 2024

that lasted for less than 1 hour after which he was able to resume his normal social and physical activities. He also reported he no longer needed to be restricted to a low salt, no alcohol and caffeine diet, and he reduced his dosage of Betahistine from 24 mg 2x/day to 16 mg 1x/day.

Conclusion: This case report shows CBP® corrective spinal rehabilitation may provide significant and sustained improvements in patients who suffer from chronic debilitating and spontaneous vertigo by improving spinal alignment and posture.

Figure 1. Pre-Treatment Lateral Full Spine (Stitched Sectionals) Radiograph

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal spinal alignment and posture. The red lines represent the actual C2-L5 posterior tangents of the patient. The large yellow numbers are the cervical, thoracic, and lumbar sagittal curvatures. The small yellow annotations are the numbered cervical, thoracic, and lumbar vertebrae.

Figure 2A-C. Pre-Treatment, B) Post-Treatment, and C) 16-Month Long-Term Follow-Up Sagittal Posture Analysis

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal posture. The red lines represent the actual sagittal posture of the patient. The yellow circles with the black ring inside are anatomical landmarks made to analyze the patient's posture.

Figure 3. CBP® Mirror Image® Corrective A-B) Adjustments, C-D) Spinal Exercises, E-F) Mechanical Traction

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Sustained Improvements of Thoracic Hyperkyphosis, Sagittal Balance, Disability, and Quality of Life in a 26-Year-Old Male with Scheuermann's Disease Using Chiropractic BioPhysics® Spinal Rehabilitation: A Case Report and 10-Month Long-Term Follow-Up.

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Abstract

Objective: To report the sustained Improvements of thoracic hyperkyphosis, sagittal balance, and health-related quality-of-life (HRQOL) in a 26-year-old male with Scheuermann's disease using Chiropractic BioPhysics® (CBP®) spinal rehabilitation with a one-year long-term follow-up.

Clinical Features: A 26-year-old male presented to a chiropractic clinic with thoracic hyperkyphosis and a diagnosis of Scheuermann's disease which disqualified him for United States Coast Guard (USCG) enlistment. Thoracic kyphosis with a Cobb angle greater than 40° is considered a disqualifying medical condition for the USCG.

The patient reported minimal mid-back pain (MBP) and low back pain (LBP) and was more concerned about his spinal alignment and posture. He rated his MBP and LBP 1/10 on a Numeric Rating Scale (NRS) where 0 is no pain and 10 is maximum pain. He completed an Oswestry Disability Index (ODI) survey to determine his self-rated disability due to LBP. The patient scored 16% (mild disability due to LBP) on a scale of 0-100% where 0 is no disability and 100 is complete disability. The patient completed a RAND 36 health-related quality of life (HRQOL) survey to determine the impact of his MBP and LBP on his quality of life (QOL) and to assess his self-rated disability. The RAND 36 is a 36-question survey that provides scaled scores for different HRQOL domains on a scale of 0 to 100, where 0 is the lowest HRQOL and 100 is the highest. Pre-treatment RAND 36 scores below normal limits showed: Bodily Pain (BP) was 37.5, Emotional Well-Being (EWB) was 48.4, Energy/Fatigue (EF) was 45.5, and General Health (GH) was 60 (Table 1).

Posture analysis was performed using PostureScreen® Mobile Posture Analysis (PostureCo, Inc., Trinity, FL, USA). Pre-treatment sagittal posture analysis showed anterior pelvic and head translation (+TzP, +TzH), posterior thorax translation (-TzT), and increased thorax flexion (+RxT) with anterior sagittal balance (Figure 1A).

Radiographic analysis was performed using PostureRay® X-Ray Electronic Health Records Software (PostureCo, Inc., Trinity, FL, USA). Pre-treatment sagittal radiographic analysis confirmed the Scheuermann's disease diagnosis and showed sagittal imbalance and hyperkyphosis of the thoracic spine with the following measurements: absolute rotational angle of T2 to T11 (ARA T2-T11) measuring 55.5° (ideal is 42°), ARA T4-L2 (max ARA) measuring 86.7° (ideal is 30), Cobb angle from T4 to T12 (Cobb T4-T12) measuring 72.5°, Cobb T4-L2 (max Cobb) measuring 82.4°, sagittal translation of T12 with respect to S1 (Tz T12-S1) measuring -111.3 mm (ideal is 0 mm), and Tz T1-T12 measuring 61.5 mm (ideal is 0 mm) (Figures 2-3A, Table 1). Stress Radiographs were taken in prone position (Figure 4) and in supine position with a Thoracic Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotic (Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotics, New South Wales, Australia) placed at the mid-to-lower thoracic spine to create thoracic extension (Figure 5). Both stress radiographs showed reduction in thoracic hyperkyphosis and improvement in sagittal balance indicating flexibility of the thoracic spine and a correction potential.

Intervention & Outcomes: The patient was treated 42 times in-office over 14 weeks. The patient received CBP® Mirror

Image® (MI) adjustments using a chiropractic drop table (Figure 6A) and instrument adjusting using an IMPAC Pro-ArthroStim® Instrument (I.M.P.A.C. Inc., Salem, OR, USA) (Figure 6B). The MI therapies involve positioning the patient in a corrected or over-corrected postural position (-TzP, +TzT, -RxT, -TzH). Sagittal MI mechanical traction was performed in supine (Figure 7A), prone (Figure 7B), and seated positions (Figure 7C). MI therapeutic exercises included floor angels (Figure 8A), leg raises while supine on the floor with a medium CBP® Mirror Image® Block (CBP Seminars, Inc., Meridian, ID, USA) placed as a fulcrum at the apex of the thoracic kyphosis (Figure 8B), prone Superman exercises on the floor with a large CBP® Mirror Image® Block under the pelvis to induce +TzT and -RxT (Figure 8C), and standing exercises with back facing the wall and a block creating a fulcrum at the apex of the thoracic kyphosis (Figure 8D). At-home therapies were prescribed for the patient including MI mechanical traction using the Thoracic Denneroll™ and therapeutic exercise using CBP® traction blocks.

A re-exam was performed following 24 CBP® MI spinal rehabilitation visits over 8 weeks. The patient rated his MBP and LBP 0/10 on the NRS. The patient scored 0% on his re-exam ODI indicating no disability due to LBP. Re-exam RAND 36 scores were improved with: BP at 50, EWB at 60.5, and EF at 60 (Table 1). Re-exam posture analysis showed improvement in sagittal posture and balance (Figure 1B). Re-exam sagittal radiographic analysis showed improvement in sagittal balance and hyperkyphosis of the thoracic spine with the following measurements: ARA T2-T11 measuring 54.9°, ARA T4-L2 (max ARA) measuring 66.8°, Cobb T4-T12 measuring 64.1°, Cobb T4-L2 (max Cobb) measuring 74.0°, and Tz T12-S1 measuring -77.4 mm (Figures 3B, Table 1).

A post-treatment exam was performed following an additional 18 CBP® MI spinal rehabilitation visits (42 visits total) over another 6 weeks (14 weeks total). The patient maintained his MBP and LBP 0/10 on the NRS. The patient scored 0% on his post-treatment ODI indicating no disability due to LBP. Post-treatment RAND 36 scores were further improved and WNL with: BP at 100, EWB at 68, EF at 90, and GH at 100 (Table 1). Post-treatment posture analysis showed continued improvement in sagittal posture and balance (Figure 1C). Post-treatment sagittal radiographic analysis showed further improvement in sagittal balance and hyperkyphosis of the thoracic spine with the following measurements: ARA T2-T11 measuring 43.8°, ARA T4-L2 (max ARA) measuring 51.3°, Cobb T4-T12 measuring 62.7°, Cobb T4-L2 (max Cobb) measuring 64.6°, Tz T12-S1 measuring -64.1 mm, and TZ T1-T12 measuring 40.3 mm (Figures 3C, Table 1).

A 10-month long-term follow-up exam was performed following an additional 23 maintenance visits and at-home therapies (65 visits total) over another 42 weeks (66 weeks total). The patient maintained his MBP and LBP 0/10 on the NRS. The patient maintained 0/100 on his ODI indicating no disability due to LBP. Long-term follow-up RAND 36 maintained scores WNL. Long-term follow-up posture analysis showed continued improvement in sagittal posture and balance (Figure 1D). Post-treatment sagittal radiographic analysis showed further improvement in sagittal balance and hyperkyphosis of the thoracic spine with the following measurements: ARA T2-T11 measuring 42.0°, ARA T4-L2 (max ARA) measuring 50.7°, Cobb T4-T12 measuring 56.1°, Cobb T4-L2 (max Cobb) measuring 59.0°, and TZ T1-T12 measuring 12.7 mm (Figures 3D, Table 1).

Conclusion: The results of this case indicate the CBP® spinal rehabilitation can be an effective method in long-term improvements in Scheuermann's disease (thoracic hyperkyphosis and abnormal sagittal posture and balance) which can cause or contribute to MBP and LBP, disability, and decreased HRQOL. Improvement in sagittal spinal alignment and posture may result in long-term reduction or resolution of MBP, LBP, and improved HRQOL. This case study shows the need for more research involving spinal rehabilitation of Scheuermann's disease and concomitant health outcome measures.

Table 1. Health Outcome Measures at Pre-Treatment, Re-Exam, Post-Treatment, and Long-Term Follow-Up Exams

Health Outcome Measure	Ideal Values	Pre-Treatment	Re-Exam (24 visits, 8 weeks)	Post-Treatment (+18 visits, 6 weeks)	Long-Term Follow-Up (+23 visits, 42 weeks)
Radiographic Mensuration					
ARA T1-T12 (°)	44	52.3	59.3	50.9	53.6
ARA T2-T11 (°)	42	55.5	54.9	43.8	42.0
ARA T3-T10 (°)	37	48.5	35.4	34.8	31.4
ARA T4-L2 (Max ARA) (°)	30	86.7	66.8	51.3	50.7
Cobb T1-T12 (°)	20-40	60.4	69.3	57.7	40.7
Cobb T4-T12 (°)		72.5	64.1	62.7	56.1
Cobb T4-L2 (Max Cobb) (°)		82.4	74.0	64.6	59.0
Tz T12-S1 (mm)	0	-111.3	-77.4	-64.1	-68.6
Tz T1-T12 (mm)	0	61.5	62.3	40.3	12.7
Patient Reported Outcomes					
NRS (LBP)	0	1	0	0	0
NRS (MBP)	0	1	0	0	0
ODI (%)	0	16	0	0	0
RAND-36 Energy/Fatigue	68-100	45.5	60.0	90	90
RAND-36 Emotional Well-Being	68-100	48.4	60.5	68	68
RAND-36 Bodily Pain	68-100	37.5	50.0	100	100
RAND-36 General Health	68-100	60.0	60.0	100	90

ARA = Absolute Rotational Angle; Cobb = Cobb angle; Tz = sagittal translation (translation in the z-axis); NRS = numeric rating scale; LBP = low back pain; MBP = mid-back pain; ODI = Oswestry disability index; NDI = neck disability index.

Figure 1. A) Pre-Treatment, B) Re-Exam, C) Post-Treatment, and D) Long-Term Follow-Up Posture Analysis

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal posture. The red lines represent the actual sagittal posture of the patient. The yellow circles with the black ring inside are anatomical landmarks made to analyze the patient's posture and the yellow dotted lines show the thoracic kyphosis and pelvic measurements.

Figure 2. Pre-Treatment Sagittal Full-Spine (Stitched Sectionals) Radiographs with Thoracic/Thoracolumbar Kyphosis Measurements

Image Features: The green continuous line with 3 curves represents a normal, ideal sagittal spinal alignment and posture. The red lines represent the actual C2-S1 posterior tangent lines of the patient. The black numbers in yellow circles are the numbered cervical, thoracic, lumbar, and sacral vertebrae. The yellow dots represent the marked C1 anatomical landmarks, anterior superior and inferior and posterior superior and inferior aspects of C2-S1 and hip anatomical landmarks. The orange lines through the vertebral endplates are the Cobb T1-T12 angle; the yellow lines through the vertebral endplates are the Cobb T4-L2 angle; the blue lines through the vertebral endplates are the Cobb T4-T12 angle; the red elongated posterior tangent lines are the ARA T1-T12; the violet posterior tangent lines are the ARA T2-T12; the purple posterior tangent lines are the ARA T3-T10; and the green posterior tangent lines are the ARA T4-L2; the red lines are the ARA T1-T12.

Figure 3. A) Pre-Treatment, B) Re-Exam, C) Post-Treatment, and D) Long-Term Follow-Up Sagittal Full-Spine (Stitched Sectionals) Radiographs

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal spinal alignment and posture. The red lines represent the C2-S1 posterior tangent lines of the patient. The black numbers in yellow circles are the numbered cervical, thoracic, lumbar, and sacral vertebrae. The yellow dots represent the marked C1 anatomical landmarks, anterior superior and inferior and posterior superior and inferior aspects of C2-S1 and hip anatomical landmarks.

Figure 4. A) Prone Positioning with Thoracic Extension for a B) Sagittal Thoracic Stress Radiograph

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal thoracic spinal alignment. The red lines represent the actual T1-T12 posterior tangent lines of the patient. The black numbers in yellow circles are the numbered thoracic vertebrae. The yellow dots represent the anterior superior and inferior and posterior superior and inferior aspects of T1-T12.

Figure 5. A) Supine Positioning on a Thoracic Denneroll™ Placed at Mid-to-Low Thoracic Spine with Thoracic Extension for a B) Sagittal Thoracic Stress Radiograph

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal thoracic and lumbar spinal alignment. The red lines represent the actual T1-S1 posterior tangent lines of the patient. The black numbers in yellow circles are the numbered thoracic vertebrae. The yellow dots represent the anterior superior and inferior and posterior superior and inferior aspects of T1-T12 and hip anatomical landmarks.

Figure 6. Sagittal Mirror Image® Chiropractic Adjustments Performed in A) Prone Position Using a Drop Table and B) Standing using an IMPAC Pro-ArthroStim® Instrument

Figure 7. Sagittal Mirror Image® Mechanical Traction Performed in A) Supine, B) Prone, and C) Seated Positions

Figure 8. Sagittal Mirror Image® Therapeutic Exercises Including: A) Floor Angels, B) Leg Raises While Supine on the Floor, C) Prone Superman Exercises on the Floor, and D) Standing Exercises Against the Wall

6

Improvement in Chronic Neck Pain and Quality of Life Following Correction of Sagittal and Frontal Spinal Alignment and Posture Using Chiropractic BioPhysics® Structural Spinal Rehabilitation: A Case Report and 6-Month Follow-Up

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Abstract

Objective: To report on the successful treatment of a patient with chronic neck pain and disability using corrective chiropractic care with a six-month follow-up. Neck pain is one of the world's leading causes of disability and missed days of work which negatively impacts the physical, emotional and financial components of the global burden of disease (GBD).

Clinical Features: A 44-year-old male presented to a chiropractic clinic with severe neck pain that he rated 8-9/10 on a Numeric Rating Scale (NRS) where 0 is no pain and 10 is maximum pain with decreased cervical range of motion. The patient completed a Short-Form 36 health-related quality of life (HRQOL) survey to determine the impact of his neck pain on his quality of life (QOL) and to assess his self-rated disability. The SF-36 is a 36-question survey that provides scaled scores for nine different HRQOL domains on a scale of 0 to 100, where 0 is the lowest HRQOL and 100 is the highest. Pre-treatment SF-36 scores showed: Physical Functioning (PF) was 80, Bodily Pain (BP) was 22.5, Role Limitations Due to Physical Health Problems (RP) was 0, Role Limitations due to Personal or Emotional Problems (RE) was 100, General Mental Health (MH) was 88, Social Functioning (SF) was 62.5, Energy/Fatigue or Vitality (VIT) was 65, and General Health (GH) was 70.

Posture analysis was performed using PostureScreen® Mobile Posture Analysis (PostureCo, Inc., Trinity, FL, USA). Pre-treatment coronal posture analysis showed left pelvic and thorax translation (+TxP, +TxT) and right head translation and rotation (-TxH, +RyH) with total coronal translations measuring 74 mm (ideal is 0 mm) and total coronal lateral flexions measuring 5.3° (ideal is 0°) (Figure 1A). Pre-treatment sagittal posture analysis showed anterior pelvic and head translation (+TzP, +TzH) and posterior thorax translation (-TzT) with total sagittal translations measuring 128 mm (ideal is 0 mm) (Figure 2A).

Radiographic analysis was performed using PostureRay® X-Ray Electronic Health Records Software (PostureCo, Inc., Trinity, FL, USA). Pre-treatment coronal radiographic analysis showed a cervical dorsal angle of right lateral flexion from C2 to T6 (CDA C2-T6) with an apex at T1 measuring 5.6° (ideal is 0°) and coronal vertical axis of C2 with respect to S1 (CVA C2-S1) measuring 8.4 mm (Figure 3A). Pre-treatment sagittal radiographic analysis showed buckling of the cervical spine with an absolute rotational angle from C2 to C7 (ARA C2-C7) measuring -7.6° (ideal is -42°) consisting of a mid-cervical kyphosis ARA C3-C6 measuring 3.6° (ideal is -24°), sagittal translation of C2 to C7 (Tz C2-C7) measuring 18.4 mm (ideal is 0 mm) and ARA T1-T12 measuring 54.2° (ideal is 44°) (Figure 4A).

Intervention & Outcomes: The patient was treated 36 times in-office over 3 months. The patient received manual Gonstead and Chiropractic BioPhysics® (CBP®) Mirror Image® (MI) adjustments using a chiropractic drop table and instrument adjusting using an Impulse® Adjusting Instrument (Neuromechanical Innovations, Chandler, AZ, USA). The MI therapies involve positioning the patient in a corrected or over-corrected postural position. Sagittal MI mechanical traction was performed using the 3-D Denneroll™ Traction Table System (Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotics, New South Wales, Australia) with the patient supine, his feet on a 3-inch block, a thoracic Denneroll™ tail down with the fulcrum at T6 and his head

hanging off the top of the table in extension and an elastic band contacting the forehead and pulling caudal inducing compression-extension. Coronal MI mechanical traction was performed using the Circular Traction XZ Traction Wall Unit (Circular Traction Supply, Inc., Huntington Beach, CA, USA) with the patient positioned -TxP, -TxT, and +TxH). Coronal MI spinal exercises were performed by the patient involving moving into and sustaining a -TxP, -TxT, and +TxH position. Sagittal MI spinal exercises were performed by the patient involving moving into and sustaining a -TzP, +TzT, and -TzH position. Core stabilizing exercises using an exercise ball and bands were also prescribed. The patient was prescribed to perform the MI spinal exercises at-home daily. The patient was also prescribed to perform at-home MI traction using a large Cervical Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotic (Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotics, New South Wales, Australia) to restore cervical lordosis.

Post-treatment posture analysis showed improvement in posture with total coronal translations measuring 37 mm, total coronal lateral flexions measuring 3.0°, and total sagittal translations measuring 93 mm (Figures 1B-2B). Post-treatment radiographic examination revealed significant improvements in CDA C2-T6 (T1 apex) to 1.5°, CVA C2-S1 to 1.7 mm, ARA C2-C7 to -31.2°, correction of the mid-cervical kyphosis ARA C3-C6 to -13.6°, Tz C2-C7 to -7.4, and ARA T1-T12 to 37.5° (Figures 3B-4B). Post-treatment SF-36 scores showed improvement in HRQOL with PF at 95, BP at 77.5, RP at 100, RE at 100, MH at 92, SF at 100, VIT at 80, and GH at 85.

Six-month follow-up posture analysis showed further improvement in posture with total coronal translations measuring 15 mm, total coronal lateral flexions measuring 0.0°, and total sagittal translations measuring 68 mm (Figures 1C-2C). Six-month follow-up SF-36 showed maintained or further improvements in HRQOL.

Conclusion: The results of this case indicate the CBP® Corrective Chiropractic Care can be an effective method in treating abnormal spinal alignment and posture which can cause or contribute to chronic neck pain, disability, and decreased HRQOL. Improvement in spinal alignment and posture may result in long-term reduction or resolution of neck pain and improved HRQOL. This case study shows the need for more research involving spinal biomechanics and rehabilitation in patients with chronic neck pain.

Figure 1A-C. Pre-Treatment, Post-Treatment, and 6-Month Follow-Up Coronal Posture Analysis

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal coronal posture. The red lines represent the actual coronal posture of the patient. The yellow circles with the black ring inside are anatomical landmarks made to analyze the patient's posture and the yellow dotted lines show the leg postural alignment.

Figure 2A-C. Pre-Treatment, Post-Treatment, and 6-Month Follow-Up Sagittal Posture Analysis

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal posture. The red lines represent the actual sagittal posture of the patient. The yellow circles with the black ring inside are anatomical landmarks made to analyze the patient's posture.

Figure 3A-C. Pre-Treatment, Post-Treatment, and 6-Month Follow-Up Coronal Full Spine (Stitched Sectionals) X-Rays

Figure 4A-C. Pre-Treatment, Post-Treatment, and 6-Month Follow-Up Sagittal Full Spine (Stitched Sectionals) X-Rays

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal coronal spinal alignment. The red lines represent the actual C2-S1 coronal spinal alignment of the patient.

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal spinal alignment. The red line represents the actual C2-L6 posterior tangent lines of the patient.

7

Reduction in Scoliosis Curve in an 11-Year-Old-Female Following Correction of Spinal Alignment and Posture using Chiropractic BioPhysics[®], Mirror Image Rehabilitation and ScoliBrace[®]: A Case Report

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Abstract

Objective: To present a case demonstrating a reduction in the scoliosis curve in a 11-year-old female following correction of posture and X-ray alignment using Chiropractic BioPhysics[®] (CBP[®]) Mirror Image[®] exercises, adjustments, traction and ScoliBrace[®] thoracolumbosacral orthosis (TLSO) (ScoliCare[®], Kogarah, New South Wales, Australia) scoliosis bracing.

Clinical Features: An 11-year-old female was referred to a chiropractic office from her grandmother's physical therapist. The 11-year-old's mother had expressed concern about her daughter's abnormal posture to the 11-year-old's grandmother who was a client of the physical therapist. Patient history revealed that the 11-year-old was diagnosed with scoliosis from the child's pediatrician and referred to a spinal surgeon. Surgery was scheduled 3 weeks out. The patient reported no pain.

The patient presented with abnormal spinal posture. Posture analysis showed the patient had right thoracic rotation, left thoracic lateral flexion, anterior head translation, and scoliosis (Figure 3). Radiographic examination and analysis revealed absolute rotational angle Calibrate from C2 to C7 (ARA C2-C7) measuring -5.6° (Figure 1A) and a lower thoracic scoliosis curve (apex T11) with a Cobb angle from T9-L2 (Cobb T9-L2) measuring 60.1° (Figure 2A).

Intervention and Outcomes: The patient was treated 18 times in 90 days and then biweekly for 180 days. The patient received CBP[®] Mirror Image[®] adjustments. The Mirror Image[®] adjustments involved de-rotation of the thoracolumbar spine and de-rotation with left translation and right lateral flexion of the thoracic spine while standing and lying on a chiropractic drop table. Mirror Image[®] adjustments were performed in left rotation and extension on the cervical spine with a handheld adjusting tool. Head weight sessions using 4 lbs. was used to increase cervical ARA and explained for daily home use. Mirror Image[®] exercises and neck extension exercises using a CBP[®] Pro-Lordotic Neck Exerciser (Chiropractic BioPhysics[®], Eagle, ID, USA) were performed and explained for home use daily. A ScoliRoll[®] (Denneroll[™] Spinal Orthotics, New South Wales, AUS) was explained for daily home use, working from 2 minutes up to 25 minutes. After five sessions ScoliRoll[®] was being utilized for 25 minutes daily. A ScoliBrace[®] was ordered and prescribed for 21 hours a day (3 hours off for sports and shower). In-brace radiograph shows the Cobb T9-L2 measuring 31.3° (Figure 2B).

Post-treatment posture analysis showed improved posture (Figure 3 and 4). Post treatment radiographic revealed improvement in ARA C2-C7 to -32.3° (Figure 1B), Cobb T9-L2 to 52.8° (Figure 2C) at 5 months and even further to 46.8° (Figure 2D) at 9-month follow-up. The patient has been instructed to continue home Mirror Image[®] exercises, head weight sessions, and ScoliRoll[®] sessions, as well as wearing the ScoliBrace[®] for as many hours as are tolerable.

Conclusion: In this case, CBP[®] corrective chiropractic, Mirror Image[®] exercises, ScoliRoll[®] spinal orthotic, head weights, and ScoliBrace[®] TLSO were an effective method to treat spinal alignment (Figure 1 & 2) and posture (Figure 3 & 4). Improvement in spinal alignment and posture may result in avoidance of spinal surgery and physical and mental health benefits due to the patient being able to continue to compete in sports having not undergone surgery. More research is needed on this topic, in terms of case studies and long-term outcomes in the scoliosis population.

Figure 1A-B. Pre- and Post-Treatment Neutral Lateral Cervical Radiographs

Image Features: The dotted green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal pediatric cervical spinal alignment. The red line represents the actual C2-C7 posterior tangent lines of the patient.

Figure 2. A) Pre-Treatment, B) In-Brace Stress View, C) 5-Month Re-Exam, D) 9-Month Re-Exam PA Thoracolumbar Radiographs

Image Features: The yellow lines represent the Cobb angles from the T9-L2 and the yellow numbers are the angular measurements of the scoliosis using these vertebral landmarks.

Figure 3A-B. Pre- and Post-Treatment AP Posture Pictures

Figure 4A-B. Pre- and Post-Treatment PA Posture Pictures

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Improvement in Chronic Headache Syndrome and Quality-of-Life Following Correction of Sagittal and Coronal Cervical Misalignment in a Patient with Sacral Morphology Utilizing Chiropractic BioPhysics® Spinal Rehabilitation and Novel Spinal Orthotic Traction Device: A Case Report with 3-Year Follow-Up

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Abstract

Objective: To present a case of successful corrective chiropractic treatment for a patient with a 10-year history of chronic headaches, neck pain, right shoulder dislocations, anxiety, depression, maintenance insomnia, mid-back pain, and decreased quality-of-life (QOL) from spinal subluxations with additional cervical improvement discovered at 3-year follow-up.

Clinical Features: A 32-year-old male presented to a chiropractic practice with a 10-year history of chronic episodic head, neck, and right shoulder pain from injury and dislocations. Right shoulder pain varied and dislocations were episodic, worsening in the past few years at 3-5 times per year. Between the ages of 12-17 the patient had numerous skateboarding injuries to his neck and head with symptoms lasting days to weeks. The patient reported a trauma that resulted in a brief loss of consciousness (LOC) and another where a go-cart ran over his head. He reported feeling quite anxious and depressed about his body pains and wondered if chronic headaches meant a shorter life span. He has received general and emergency medical care for his injuries and symptoms, but his symptoms and poor QOL persisted.

The patient rated his headaches and neck pain 6-7/10 (on a Numeric Rating Scale (NRS) where 0 is none and 10 is max) and right shoulder pain 8/10. Headache frequency was 2-3 days/week for the first 8 years and increased to daily for the last 2 years. The patient completed patient reported outcomes (PRO) to assess disability and QOL. Pre-treatment headache disability inventory (HDI) total score was 92/100 (emotional component 46/52 and functional component 46/48; complete disability) where 0 is no disability and 100 is maximum disability due to headaches. Short Form 36-question QOL survey (SF-36) provides scaled scores for nine different HRQOL domains on a scale of 0 to 100, where 0 is the lowest HRQOL and 100 is the highest. Pre-treatment SF-36 scores showed: Role Limitations Due to Physical Health Problems (RP) was 0, Role Limitations due to Emotional Problems (RE) was 33.33, Energy (E) was 35, Emotional Well-Being (MH) was 44, Social Functioning (SF) was 50, Bodily Pain (BP) was 45, General Health (GH) was 30, and Change in Health Status (Δ H) was 25.

Posture analysis was performed using PostureScreen® Mobile Posture Analysis (PostureCo, Inc. Trinity, FL, USA) and revealed abnormal global posture of the head, rib cage, pelvis, and right ankle valgus. Radiographic examination was analyzed using PostureRay® X-Ray Electronic Health Records Software (PostureCo, Inc., Trinity, FL, USA). Pre-treatment sagittal radiographs (Figures 1A-4A) revealed 3rd order buckling of the cervical spine with cervical kyphosis from C3-5 and an Absolute Rotation Angle from C2 to C7 vertebrae (ARA C2-C7) measuring -6.6° (ideal is -42.0°). Sagittal translation of the cervical spine from C2-C7 (Tz C2-C7) measured 10 mm (ideal is 0 mm), ARA T1-T12 measured 29.5° indicating thoracic hypokyphosis (ideal is 44.0°), Tz T1- T12 measured 22.5 mm (ideal is 0 mm), ARA L1-L5 measured -31.0° indicating lumbar hypolordosis (ideal is -46.5° due to lumbosacral transitional vertebra), Tz L1-S1 measured 11.3 mm (ideal is 0 mm), and sagittal vertical axis from C1 to S1 (SVA C1-S1) measured 38.1 mm (ideal is 0 mm). Pre-treatment coronal radiographs

(Figures 5A-6A) revealed Euler buckling in the AP cervical spine with a cervicodorsal angle from C2 to C7 (CDA C2-C7) measuring 7.4° with a C5 apex (ideal is 0°), coronal translation of C2 to T7 (Tx C2-T7) measuring -9.2 mm (ideal is 0 mm), Euler buckling in the AP thoracic spine from T4 to T12 measuring -4.6°, lumbodorsal angle T12 to L5 (LDA T12-L5) measuring 3.5°, lumbospinal angle from T12 to L5 (LSA T12-L5) -87.8° (ideal is 90°), and Tx T12-S1 measuring 3.2 mm (ideal is 0 mm). The right shoulder was diagnosed with unspecific rotator cuff pathology with chronic inflammation from dislocations.

Intervention & Outcomes: The patient completed 37 sessions of in-office visits of Chiropractic BioPhysics® (CBP®) spine rehabilitation at a frequency of 3 times per week for 3 months consisting of chiropractic Diversified manipulation and cryotherapy (PRN), specific CBP® Mirror Image® (MI) adjustments (using drop-table and instrument), spinal exercises (Figure 7A-B), and mechanical traction (Figure 7C-D). MI therapies involved placing the patient in their corrected or over-corrected postural position with use of the 3-D Denneroll™ Traction Table System (Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotics, New South Wales, Australia), Erickson Traction Fulcrum (Circular Traction Supply, Inc., Huntington Beach, CA, USA), Total Target Force Counterstress Traction Unit (Promote Chiropractic, Inc., Saugus, MA, USA), and a novel coronal cervical orthotic traction device (Figure 8). Class IV deep tissue LightForce® laser therapy (LiteCure, LLC, New Castle, DE, USA) was also performed 10 minutes on each region (cervical spine and right rotator cuff) for 5 sessions in week 1 and 2. He reported no incidence of right shoulder dislocations after the first 2 weeks of treatment and stated that he felt his shoulder strengthen and began to work out again by weeks 4 and 5. At-home ergonomic instructions were given: avoid looking down (e.g. cell phone use) and sleep with a cervical roll.

Following the 37 in-office visits, post-treatment radiographs were taken and analyzed. Post-treatment sagittal radiographs (Figures 1B-4B) revealed correction of the cervical spine with a full lordosis and an ARA C2-C7 measuring -17.4°, Tz C2-C7 measuring -9.7, ARA T1-T12 measuring 29.3°, Tz T1-T12 measured -19.6 mm, ARA L1-L5 measuring -36.5°, Tz L1-S1 measured 3.9 mm, and SVA C1-S1 measured -36.7 mm. Post-treatment coronal radiographs (Figures 5B-6B) revealed correction of CDA C2-C7 measuring 3.2°, Tx C2-T7 measuring -5.9 mm, Euler buckling in the AP thoracic spine from T4 to T12 measuring -4.0°, LDA T12-L5 measuring 4.3°, LSA T12-L5 -86.8°, and Tx T12-S1 measuring 4.5 mm. Post-treatment HDI total score improved to 18/100 (emotional component 6/52 and functional component 12/48; mild disability). Post-treatment SF-36 scores showed improvements in: RP to 100, RE to 100, E to 80, MH to 88, SF to 100, BP to 90, GH to 75, and ΔH to 100.

After the 37 in-office visits, the patient elected to discontinue supervised care and continue with at-home care. In the 3 years following office treatment, the patient stated he would use the novel cervical coronal cervical orthotic traction device for 5-10 minutes when he felt increased neck tension (1-2 times/week) or else it would result in a headache. He stated the only complaints he feels is a mild headache once a month for 1-2 hours. Three-year follow-up posture analysis showed improved posture in both planes. Three-year follow-up radiographic diagnoses revealed additional sagittal and coronal spinal alignment improvements. Three-year follow-up sagittal radiographs (Figures 1C-4C) revealed maintained cervical spine lordosis and an ARA C2-C7 measuring -28.3°, Tz C2-C7 measuring -9.5, ARA T1-T12 measuring 42.0°, Tz T1-T12 measured 4.9 mm, ARA L1-L5 measuring -36.3°, Tz L1-S1 measured 2.0 mm, and SVA C1-S1 measured -15.5 mm. Three-year follow-up coronal radiographs (Figures 5C-6C) revealed correction of CDA C2-C7 measuring 0.1°, Tx C2-T7 measuring 0.8 mm, LDA T12-L5 measuring 6.2°, LSA T12-L5 -89.0°, and Tx T12-S1 measuring 3.4 mm (ideal is 0 mm). Three-year follow-up HDI total score improved to 2/100 (emotional component 0/52 and functional component 2/48; minimal disability). Three-year follow-up SF-36 scores showed maintained improvements in: RP at 100, RE at 100, E at 90, MH at 88, SF at 100, BP at 90, GH at 75, and ΔH at 100.

Conclusion: The results of this case demonstrate that CBP® spinal rehabilitation care using MI spinal rehabilitation may be an effective method to treat abnormal spinal alignment (vertebral subluxation) and posture which contribute to chronic pain, disability, and decreased QOL. Chronic rotator cuff inflammation from old injuries may be helped by class IV laser therapy, chiropractic manipulation, MI adjustments, and by the relationship between shoulder girdle realignment and healthy spinal alignment and posture. Corrections in spinal alignment, posture, and improved QOL outcomes may continue improving beyond the treatment phase due to the healing time associated with remodeling of spinal ligaments and associated soft tissues. This study demonstrates the effective use of a novel cervical orthotic traction device for coronal misalignment and indicates the need for more research involving spinal biomechanics and rehabilitation in

patients with disability due to cervical coronal misalignments. This case study is also a unique clinical look at treatment of a patient with a lumbosacral transitional segment and when combined with other similar cases could offer a possible predictive range for the population with his LSTV type and incident angles.

Figure 1A-C. Pre-Treatment, Post-Treatment, and 3-Year Follow-Up Neutral Lateral Cervical Radiographs

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal cervical spinal alignment. The red lines represent the actual C2-T1 posterior tangent lines of the patient.

Figure 2A-C. Pre-Treatment, Post-Treatment, and 3-Year Follow-Up Lateral Thoracic Radiographs

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal thoracic spinal alignment. The red lines represent the actual T1-T12 posterior tangent lines of the patient.

Figure 3A-C. Pre-Treatment, Post-Treatment, and 3-Year Follow-Up Lateral Lumbar Radiographs

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal lumbar spinal alignment. The red lines represent the actual L1-L6 posterior tangent lines of the patient. The yellow arrow and text are annotating the L6-S1 lumbosacral transitional vertebra.

Figure 4A-C. Pre-Treatment, Post-Treatment, and 3-Year Follow-Up Neutral Full-Spine (Stitched Sectionals) Radiographs

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal spinal alignment. The red lines represent the actual C2-L6 posterior tangent lines of the patient.

Figure 5A-C. Pre-Treatment, Post-Treatment, and 3-Year Follow-Up Lateral Lumbar Radiographs

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal coronal cervical spinal alignment. The red line represents the actual C2-T7 coronal spinal alignment of the patient.

Figure 6A-C. Pre-Treatment, Post-Treatment, and 3-Year Follow-Up Neutral Full-Spine (Stitched Sectionals) Radiographs

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal coronal spinal alignment. The red lines represent the actual C2-S1 coronal spinal alignment of the patient.

Figure 7. CBP® Mirror Image® Corrective A-B) Spinal Exercises, C-D) Mechanical Traction

9

Positive Outcomes Following Cervical Acceleration-Deceleration (CAD) Injury Using Chiropractic BioPhysics® Methods: A Pre-Auto Injury and Post-Auto Injury Case Series [Re-Print from Journal of Clinical Medicine <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm12196414>]

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Abstract

This series illustrates how rear-end impact motor vehicle collisions (MVCs) alter the cervical spine's alignment and demonstrates therapeutic use of cervical extension traction to improve lordotic alignment and other outcomes. This is a retrospective reporting of 7 adult patients (4 males and 3 females, 28–42 years) treated for cervical hypolordosis [Table 1]. These subjects received Chiropractic BioPhysics® (CBP®) rehabilitation and then were involved in a rear-end MVC. All cases had radiographic assessment that quantified the buckling of the cervical spine, presumably resulting directly from the CAD trauma [Figure 1]. After an average of 3 years and 9 months (range: 1–7.6 years) following their initial program of care [Table 2], the 7 patients sought care for a second time after the MVC. At this time, compared with their previously recorded post-treatment spine radiographs [Table 3], there was an average 18.7° (range: 7.6–35.4°) reduction in cervical lordosis, a 9.2 mm (range: 3.6–19.8 mm) increase in anterior head translation (AHT), an 11.3° (range: 0.2–19.9°) decrease in the atlas plane line (APL), as well as a 35.7% (range: 22–52%) average neck disability index score (NDI) measured after the MVC. After the crash, a second round of CBP rehabilitation was administered, resulting in an average 15.1° improvement in cervical lordosis, 10.9 mm reduction in AHT, 10.4° increase in APL, and a 23.7% drop in NDI after an average of 35 treatments over 9 weeks [Table 4]. Treatment was universally successful, as an average 80% re-establishment of the lordosis toward its pre-injury state was found. There were no adverse events reported. This case series demonstrates that motor vehicle collisions may alter the alignment of the cervical spine. Rehabilitation of the cervical curve using extension traction improved the patients' initial pre-crash alignments toward their pre-injury alignments and was likely responsible for improvement in the patients' conditions. Clinical trials are needed to confirm these findings.

Table 1. Patient demographic and symptom data.

	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6	Case 7
Age (year)	42	28	39	34	52	32	36
Sex	M	F	M	F	M	F	M
Height (cm)	185.4	154.9	182.9	170.2	190.5	162.6	175.3
Weight (kg)	74.8	81.6	99.8	74.8	88.5	63.5	86.2
BMI (kg/m ²)	21.8	34	29.8	25.8	24.4	24	28.1
First txt complaints	LBP	LBP, HA	NKP, LBP	NKP, LBP, HA	LBP	NKP	NKP, LBP, HA
Post-collision complaints	NKP, HA	NKP, HA	NKP, LBP	NKP, HA	NKP, LBP, HA	NKP, HA	NKP, LBP

LBP = low back pain; NKP = neck pain, HA = headaches.

Figure 1A-D. Pre-Rehabilitation, Post-Rehabilitation, Post-MVC, Post-MVC Rehabilitation Lateral Cervical Radiographs

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal cervical spinal alignment. The red lines represent the actual C2-C7 posterior tangent lines of the patient.

Table 2. Pre- and Post-Rehabilitation Cervical Radiographic Parameters and Neck Disability From First Trial of Rehabilitation (Prior to Later Motor Vehicle Collision).

		Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6	Case 7	Avg (SD)
Pre-rehab	ARA	-12.5°	-0.7°	-11.7°	-23.0°	-14.8°	-5.9°	-23.7°	-13.2° (8.4°)
	TzH	13.6 mm	21.6 mm	17.2 mm	18.6 mm	35.6 mm	23.3 mm	20.6 mm	21.5 mm (7.0 mm)
	APL	-13.9°	-14.4°	-25.6°	-17.7°	-17.6°	-14.1°	-21.4°	-17.8° (4.4°)
	NDI	0%	0%	18%	52%	0%	30%	62%	23.1% (25.9%)
	Pain	0/10	0/10	5/10	5/10	4/10	6/10	7/10	3.9/10 (2.8)
	HA pain	0/10	4/10	0/10	7/10	0/10	0/10	3-4/10	* 4.8/10 (1.9)
		Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6	Case 7	Avg (SD)
Txt details	No./time	35/9 w	35/9 w	23/6 w	35/9 w	35/9 w	35/9 w	47/12 w	35/9 w
	Post-rehab	ARA	-37.6°	-26.3°	-36.0°	-36.6°	-35.4°	-31.7°	-29.8°
	TzH	8.1 mm	18.3 mm	1.9 mm	9.2 mm	16.6 mm	17.2 mm	12 mm	11.9 mm (6.0 mm)
	APL	-23.9°	-27.3°	-34.0°	-28.3°	-28.4°	-25.7°	-25.1°	-27.5° (3.3°)
	NDI	0%	0%	2%	8%	0%	10%	16%	5.1% (6.3%)
	Pain	0/10	0/10	0/10	2/10	1/10	0/10	1.5/10	0.6/10 (0.9)
	HA pain	0/10	0/10	0/10	0/10	0/10	0/10	0/10	0/10 (0.0)

ARA = C2-7 absolute rotation angle, TzH = forward head posture, APL = atlas plane line, NDI = neck disability index, HA = headache. *Average of those with headaches (n = 3).

Table 3. Pre- and Post-Motor Vehicle Collision Rehabilitation Cervical Radiographic Parameters and Neck Disability.

		Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6	Case 7	Avg (SD)
Pre-MVC (Post-rehab)	ARA	-37.6°	-26.3°	-36.0°	-36.6°	-35.4°	-31.7°	-29.8°	-33.3° (4.2°)
	TzH	8.1 mm	18.3 mm	1.9 mm	9.2 mm	16.6 mm	17.2 mm	12.0 mm	11.9 mm (6.0 mm)
	APL	-23.9°	-27.3°	-34.0°	-28.3°	-28.4°	-25.7°	-25.1°	-27.5° (3.3°)
	NDI	0%	0%	2%	8%	0%	10%	16%	5.1% (6.3%)
	Pain	0/10	0/10	0/10	2/10	1/10	0/10	1-2/10	0.6/10 (0.9)
	HA pain	0/10	0/10	0/10	0/10	0/10	0/10	0/10	0/10 (0)
		Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6	Case 7	Avg (SD)
Time lapse	Year, month	7 years, 7 months	5 years, 5 months	1 year	3 years, 4 months	3 years, 6 months	2 years, 1 months	3 years, 3 months	3 years, 9 months
Post-MVC (Pre-2nd rehab)	ARA	-17.7°	+9.1°	-20.3°	-18.1°	-15.4°	-17.3°	-22.2°	-14.6° (10.7°)
	TzH	18.7 mm	26.6 mm	11.3 mm	12.8 mm	36.4 mm	21.2 mm	20.9 mm	21.1 mm (8.5 mm)
	APL	-10.6°	-7.4°	-23.3°	-14.8°	-12.8°	-25.5°	-18.7°	-16.2° (6.7°)
	NDI	26%	26%	22%	48%	40%	36%	52%	35.7% (11.6%)
	Pain	7/10	8/10	3.5/10	6/10	5/10	5/10	7/10	5.9/10 (1.5)
	HA pain	7.5/10	2.5/10	0/10	6/10	7.5/10	2.5/10	0/10	* 5.2/10 (2.5)

ARA = C2-7 absolute rotation angle, TzH = forward head posture, APL = atlas plane line, NDI = neck disability index; HA = headache. *Average of those with headaches (n = 5).

Table 4. Pre-MVC and post-MVC Rehabilitation Cervical Radiographic Parameters and Neck Disability From Second Trial of Rehabilitation After Motor Vehicle Collision.

		Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6	Case 7	Avg (SD)
Post-MVC (Pre-2nd rehab)	ARA	-17.7°	+9.1°	-20.3°	-18.1°	-15.4°	-17.3°	-22.2°	-14.6° (10.7°)
	TzH	18.7 mm	26.6 mm	11.3 mm	12.8 mm	36.4 mm	21.2 mm	20.9 mm	21.1 mm (8.5 mm)
	APL	-10.6°	-7.4°	-23.3°	-14.8°	-12.8°	-25.5°	-18.7°	-16.2° (6.7°)
	NDI	26%	26%	22%	48%	40%	36%	52%	35.7% (11.6%)
	Pain	7/10	8/10	3.5/10	6/10	5/10	5/10	7/10	5.9/10 (1.5)
		Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6	Case 7	Avg (SD)
	HA pain	7.5/10	2.5/10	0/10	6/10	7.5/10	2.5/10	0/10	* 5.2/10 (2.5)
Txt details	No./time	23/6 w	51/13 w	23/6 w	23/6 w	35/9 w	36/9 w	51/13 w	34.6/8.9 w
Post-MVC rehab	ARA	-30.0°	-14.0°	-37.8°	-28.6°	-35.1°	-32.7°	-30.0°	-29.7° (7.7°)
	TzH	11.7 mm	10.3 mm	-3.7 mm	15.5 mm	11.8 mm	13.9 mm	11.6 mm	10.2 mm (6.3 mm)
	APL	-20.1°	-21.9°	-36.1°	-19.1°	-23.9°	-35.0°	-29.8°	-26.6° (7.1°)
	NDI	0%	8%	10%	22%	20%	12%	12%	12% (7.4%)
	Pain	1.5/10	0/10	0.5/10	1/10	0.5/10	1/10	0.5/10	0.6/10 (0.5)
	HA pain	0/10	0/10	0/10	0/10	0/10	0/10	0/10	0/10 (0.0)

ARA = C2-7 absolute rotation angle, TzH = forward head posture, APL = atlas plane line, NDI = neck disability index; HA = headache. *Average of those with headaches (n = 5).